

Static Experimental to Justify the Vibration of the propeller shaft due to its unbalance

Radi Suradi.K¹, Carolus Bintoro², Vicky Wuwung³, Zaim S.I⁴

¹Mechanical Department, Polytechnics Negeri Bandung, radisk@polban.ac.id

²Mechanical Department, 3 3 Polytechnics Negeri Bandung, bintoroe@polban.ac.id

³Mechanical Department, Polytechnics Negeri Bandung,, vicky.wuwung@polban.ac.id

⁴Mechanical Department, Polytechnics Negeri Bandung, zaim.sidqi@polban.ac.id

Author Correspondence: Jl. Gegerkalong Hilir, Ciwaruga, Kec, Parompong Kabupaten Bandung Barat, Jawa Barat, Telephone 082126801733, Email address bintoroe@polban.ac.id

Abstract

This paper reports the mass imbalance in a propeller studied theoretically, experimentally, with blades made of aluminum. These propellers have been used in aircraft engines to generate thrust and for other needs, for example as a force generator for aircraft maneuvering needs. This research was completed using a half car model running on a rough track to model heaving and pitching movements. Modeling these imperfections, in this research to model an imperfect propeller shaft. A rough path in the bearing contact path is a source of excitation that causes vibration to occur. In this research, information was obtained that with wear on rolling bearings, the frequency response will produce harmonics at higher frequencies. In the propeller shaft model, the shaft modeling is similar to using a 4 degrees of freedom half car model. However, the excitation comes from an unbalanced propeller. In this case the propeller will be used as a test tool which rotates at 100 rpm. This is to provide the ability to balance statically and/or dynamically or use IoT. The vibration response is obtained by simulation in the software. If such maintenance equipment is available, and all conditions of bearing stiffness, damping and mass are in a state of precise determination, then the teaching becomes more perfect. The research helps aircraft mechanical engineers determine vibration response. Our dynamic propeller laboratory dreams of creating a lab. Static and dynamic with controllers using IoT

Keywords: *Mass Unbalanced; Vibration imbalance; aluminium propeller; Stiffness bearing; Vibration response.*

1. Introduction

Many industrial machines, including manufacturing machinery, produce vibrations in radial and translational directions. An airplane propeller is a rotating machine that produces thrust to maneuver in the air. The ability to rotate is an advantage, but vibration can affect the effectiveness of a machine, especially excessive vibration which can result in reduced propeller life. [1-2]

In fact, vibrations in industrial or aviation components are multi-axis, both in the form of heaving movements and pitching movements. [3] Therefore, the study of the vibration characteristics that occur in a machine is very important [4]. Therefore, in research that examines the manufacture of balancing machines for student practicum, static studies must be able to be studied with this practice.

The characteristics of vibration response in the presence of unbalance are the basis of research for active balance control, which is an important method in vibration monitoring and control [5]. Vibrations that occur in machine elements can be found in almost different conditions in terms of amplitude, frequency and other characteristics of the rotating machine. [6] Rotating machines are generally used in mechanical and electromechanical systems that include rotors and engines.

Gennadiy Filimonikhin(2021) has reported theoretically investigated propeller blade aerodynamic imbalances, as well as mass corrections to balance them.[7] Ehzan Safari, in his writing states the aeroelastic response of wings that have a propeller system with an unbalanced rotating mass. [8] Zhang T, (2021) stated in his article the validation and assessment of propellers for propelling aircraft. Numerical methods and simulation strategies are presented, including stable/unsteady high-fidelity computational fluid dynamics (CFD) simulations and simpler momentum-based methods. [9] And other studies from increasingly advanced researchers.

Giulia Chirico, et.al., has installed a propeller on a twin-engine turboprop aircraft and then analyzed its quiet condition in cruising flight conditions. The research has been supported by computational fluid dynamics (CFD) which investigates near-field acoustics and transfer functions to justify interior cabin noise. Synchronization has proven to be beneficial for co-rotating propellers, especially with regard to interior noise, due to its beneficial effect on the interaction between the direct sound field of the propeller and the noise caused by the fuselage. An angle closer to the maximum relative blade shift turned out to be the best choice, but resulted in a higher sound level compared to a top-in layout that rotates in the opposite direction. [10] So in this case it is proven that dynamic research is complicated, and requires detailed handling.

Propellers are rotating machines, generally used to move and maneuver aircraft in the air. The propeller works by moving air, pulling it backwards (action), this air movement then causes the plane to be pushed forward from the resulting pressure difference (reverse reaction). The more air that is pulled behind the propeller, the greater the thrust produced. Because it is so important for education, this test device was made.

2. Modeling

2.1 Unbalanced propeller and vibration

- Propellers are not only used in airplanes, but for various needs in society. The propellers include axial fan impellers, and wind turbine fans, etc. [11] Unbalance and misalignment of the rotor mass are the two main sources of propeller vibration. [12] This research is an attempt to investigate the vibration characteristics of a rotating mechanical system, which has an unbalanced rotor mounted on a protruding shaft. The vibration signal is the result of a simulation on the Matlab Simulink device which is generated in propeller conditions and installed in the bearing housing with irregular bearing housing conditions. The irregularity of the bearing housing can be described as follows:

Fig. 1 Topography of the rough profiles $ZL(x)$ [10]

If the waviness of the bearing is described in 2 d, a curve can be obtained which can be approximated by the Fourier 8 model function with the following constants:

$$y(x) = a_0 + a_1 \cos(x*w) + b_1 \sin(x*w) + a_2 \cos(2*x*w) + b_2 \sin(2*x*w) + a_3 \cos(3*x*w) + b_3 \sin(3*x*w) + a_4 \cos(4*x*w) + b_4 \sin(4*x*w) + a_5 \cos(5*x*w) + b_5 \sin(5*x*w) + a_6 \cos(6*x*w) + b_6 \sin(6*x*w) + a_7 \cos(7*x*w) + b_7 \sin(7*x*w) + a_8 \cos(8*x*w) + b_8 \sin(8*x*w)$$

Table 1 Coefficients (with 95% confidence bounds):

N	A	B
0	0.05121	
1	-0.09767	0.001261
2	0.08222	-0.001665
3	-0.06163	0.0005001
4	0.04048	-0.00134
5	-0.02278	0.001336
6	0.01028	-0.0009082
7	-0.003095	0.0005815
8	0.0009216	8.75e-005
w	4.176e+004	

This profile occurs due to continuous external loads and less than perfect storage conditions. This topographic condition occurs due to undulations, waviness and roughness in the bearing as seen in Fig.2. [13]

Bearing conditions like those in Fig.3 are often found, even though they are actually μm in size in daily use.

Fig. 2 The waviness profile of the propeller shaft bearing

In Fig. 4, you can observe the condition of the propeller with 5 blades, which is a modeling of the existence of an unbalanced mass as far as the point of rotation on its axis. The imbalance condition is then transferred to the shaft between the 2 bearings as a force and moment. These forces and moments are then damped by the bearing housing and its seat. This point is the focus of the research.

Fig. 3 Propeller with 5 blades and unbalanced mass

2.2 Real propeller condition

This research begins with dismantling the propeller from an airplane. After that, measurements were carried out to see the possibility of placing a holder with resin-rubber as the holder, to be used as a propeller test device as a practical material.

Fig. 4 The propeller is still on the airplane

After successful disassembly of the blade, it is then analyzed so that it is known that some inconsistencies must be corrected. This is true to ensure that unbalance and aircraft safety problems can be met, and student test devices can be produced. [15-17]

In unbalance conditions, it is clear that there is a classification in the propeller process.[18] The mass of the propeller is included in the measurement rules, to determine the uniformity of the weight. From the measurement results, it turns out that one of the blades weighs 0.1 kg less than the other blade.

From the weighing results, it is known that only 1 blade has a different weight from the other blades. The weight of the three blades is 7.46 kg, 7.46 kg, and 7.36 kg. It is clear that there is an imbalance of 0.10 kg which can cause an imbalance of $0.10 \cdot \omega^2 \cdot R \cdot \cos \omega \cdot t$.

2.3 4 dof system shaft holder model

From this research, complexity was carried out by changing to a 4 dof system. In Fig.9, Z_s , Z_1 , Z_2 , Z_{front} , Z_{rear} , are the vertical displacements of the shaft, mass bearing 1, mass bearing 2, and front seat 1, and rear seat 2. Vertical performance for simulating the up and down movement of a shaft due to imbalance. excitation can be overcome by being represented with a 4 dof model as shown in Fig. 9. [19] In the last decade, many studies have utilized vehicle suspension motion in vibration system engineering, and in this case will be applied to correct propeller imbalance. [20]

From the use of the vibration model as can be seen in Fig. 9, the equation of motion can be written as follows:

Fig. 5 Model getaran yang digunakan dalam penelitian

$$[M]\{\ddot{x}\} + [C]\{\dot{x}\} + [K]\{x\} = \{f\} \quad \dots\dots\dots (7)$$

Where the matrix is composed of the following components,

$$[M] = \begin{bmatrix} m_g & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & I_s & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & m_{uf} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & m_{ur} \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

$$[C] = \begin{bmatrix} c_{sr} + c_{sr} & c_{sr}l_1 + c_{sf}l_2 & -c_{sr} & -c_{sf} \\ c_{sr}l_2 + c_{sf}l_1 & c_{sr}l_2^2 + c_{sf}l_1^2 & -c_{sr}l_2 & -c_{sf}l_1 \\ -c_{sr} & -c_{sr}l_2 & c_{sr} & 0 \\ -c_{sf} & -c_{sf}l_1 & 0 & c_{sf} \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

$$[K] = \begin{bmatrix} k_{sf} + k_{sr} & k_{sr}l_1 & -k_{sr} & -k_{sf} \\ k_{sr}l_2 + k_{sf}l_1 & k_{sr}l_2^2 + k_{sf}l_1^2 & -k_{sr}l_2 & -k_{sf}l_1 \\ -k_{sr} & -k_{sr}l_2 & k_{sr} + k_{tr} & 0 \\ -k_{sf} & -k_{sf}l_1 & 0 & k_{sf} + k_{tf} \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots\dots\dots (10)$$

$$[F] = \begin{bmatrix} f_y \\ M_y \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

$$\{X\} = \begin{Bmatrix} x_s \\ \theta_s \\ x_{sr} \\ x_{sf} \end{Bmatrix} \dots\dots\dots (12)$$

As previously written, the propeller stand system can be arranged using 4 dof modeling. This system can work with the quantities as stated in the Nomenclature.

By using the values above, the expected vibration response will be obtained. The values above were obtained from the results of reviewing other people's research obtained through digital numerical studies. This value includes stiffness values obtained from high speed to 50 Hz rotation

3. Simulation

In the simulation vibration method with this matrix and with values for each parameter, and vibration variables with different parameter quantities, were not studied in this research.

Fig. 6 Value of bearing stiffness [17]

By providing the above values, the expected vibration response will be obtained. The values above were obtained from other people's research results obtained by digital numerical studies. This value includes the stiffness value obtained from high speed up to a By using interpolation and data processing using software, stiffness $k_b = 5.463 \times 10^7$ N/m. rotation speed of 50 Hz

By using interpolation and data processing using software, stiffness $k_b = 5.463 \times 10^7$ N/m.

Fig. 7 Damping roller bearings [21]

4. DISCUSSION

Application of computational studies of the data in Figs. 8, it can be obtained that the damping on a 50 Hz rotation is $8.12 \cdot 10^3$ N.m/s.

From the simulation above with waviness in the bearing contact with the shaft and without waviness it can be resolved. From the simulation with a rotation of 100 RPM or 3000 RPM, it is known that the response size occurs at a size of μm so that the measuring instrument used is an accelerometer which is capable of measuring this size.

Vibration response without waviness and within 100 RPM rotation

Fig. 8 Vibration response curve of the propeller shaft vibration model without waviness and with a rotation of 100 rpm.

Fig. 9 Vibration response curve of the propeller shaft vibration model without waviness and with a rotation of 3000 rpm

This simulation at 3000 rpm produces 0.1184 at the pitching peak and 0.0003242 at the heaving peak. And when compared to 100 rpm rotation it produces 0.0406 at peak pithing and 0.001679 at peak heaving.

Fig. 10 Vibration response curve for propeller shaft vibration model with waviness and 100 rpm rotation

5. CONCLUSION

In this chapter the researcher discusses the research conclusions. In this case the author understands that vibration is very dependent on excitation force so that if there is unbalance in the propeller, the excitation will be transmitted to other components, including the bearing housing.

Because the displacement in the roller bearing occurs around 10^{-4} - 10^{-5} m, a dynamic vibration measuring instrument is needed which can describe vibrations that occur at low frequencies.

This unbalance test device can be used for static vibration, where it can directly show the response.

6. Nomenclature

Table 2 Terms used in this research

Term	Implication	Values
f_y	Vertical forced	from the unbalanced forced
M_y	Shaft moment	Unbalanced force transfer
x_s	Def. shaft	Heaving shaft
θ_s	Rot. shaft	Pitching shaft
x_{sr}	Angular shaft front	$l_1 * \theta$
x_{sf}	Angular shaft rear	$l_2 * \theta$
k	stiffness	
k_{sr}	stiff. Rear shaft	5.463. 107 N/m
k_{sf}	stiff. Front shaft	5.463. 107 N/m
k_{tr}	stiff. Rear seat	1 104 N/mm
k_{tf}	Stiff. Front seat	1 104 N/mm
l_1	Front arm	250 mm
l_2	Rear arm	250 mm
C	Matrix Damping	
c_{sr}	Damp. Rear str	8.12 10 ³ N.m/s
c_{sf}	Damp. Front str	8,12 103 N.m/s
M	Matrik mass	
m_g	Str. Mass	0.1 Kg
I_s	Str. Inetia	2,11 10 ⁻⁵ Kg.m2
m_{uf}	Front bearing seat	700 gr
m_{ur}	Rear bearing seat	700 gr

Funding

This work was supported by Politeknik Negeri Bandung as part of 2023 Laboratory Expansion Research Program.

Conflict of Interests

All authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest

Acknowledgment

I am very happy and proud of this work from UPPM Politeknik Negeri Bandung. Designing and making this practical tool will develop students' understanding of theoretical and practical understanding. Each of the members of my research committee has provided me extensive personal and professional guidance and taught me a great deal about both scientific research and life in general.

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